

Preparation and Characterisation of Aluminium(III) Aryloxides

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Compounds of composition $AlCl_3(OC_6H_5)_3$, $AlCl(OC_6H_5)_3$ and $Al(Oaryl)_3$ have been prepared by reacting aluminium(III) chloride with phenol in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 ratio and with *o*-nitrophenol and *o*-chlorophenol and triphenylcarbinol in 1 : 3 molar ratio. These products have been characterised by elemental analysis, cryoscopic studies, conductance and ir spectral studies.

AS compared to metal alkoxides¹, less attention has been directed towards the chemistry of the closely related metal derivatives of phenol²⁻⁴. The substitution of alkyl by phenyl group introduces new electronic and steric influences worthy of examination and might well modify properties which are important in many industrial applications of these compounds. An attempt has, therefore, been made to isolate and characterise the aryloxides of aluminium(III) and compare their properties with the alkoxides.

Experimental

Organic solvents were purified by standard methods.

Aluminium(III) phenoxide was prepared by different routes. (i) Aluminium(III) chloride (1.10 g, 0.082 mol) was refluxed with excess of phenol (30 g) till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The solid so obtained was washed with benzene to remove excess phenol and dried. (ii) Aluminium(III) chloride (2.34 g, 0.017 mol) was refluxed with phenol (4.95 g, 0.052 mol) in benzene (30 ml). The refluxing was continued for more than 48 h till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The solid so obtained was filtered washed with benzene and dried. (iii) Aluminium sulphide, Al_2S_3 , (1.50 g, 0.0083 mol) was refluxed with excess phenol (3.09 g, 0.032 mol) in xylene. The reaction was complete when there was no evolution of hydrogen sulphide gas. The solid so obtained was dried. (iv) In the alcohol-phenol interchange method, aluminium isopropoxide was prepared by the method reported by Mehrotra⁵. Aluminium isopropoxide (2 g) was suspended in dry benzene (50 ml) and then dry phenol (6 g, 0.063 mol) was added. The mixture was refluxed over low flame for 48 h. It was observed that the colour and texture of aluminium isopropoxide completely changed. The contents

were then filtered under anhydrous conditions and washed with dry benzene to remove excess phenol and finally washed with dry ether (b.p. 40-60°) and finally dried under dry atmosphere (Found : 8.60. Calcd. 8.82%).

$Al(OC_6H_4NO_2)_3$ was prepared by different routes. (i) Aluminium(III) chloride (0.802 g, 0.0060 mol) with excess of *o*-nitrophenol (30 g, 0.021 mol) in benzene (100 ml) for more than 48 h till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The compound so obtained was filtered, washed and dried. (ii) Al_2S_3 (1.50 g, 0.010 mol) was refluxed with excess *o*-nitrophenol (5.282 g, 0.038 mol) in xylene for 48 h. The compound so obtained was washed with xylene and dried under dry atmosphere. (iii) Aluminium chloride (2.30 g, 0.016 mol, was refluxed with sodium *o*-nitrophenoxide (8.3 g) 0.051 mol) in benzene (100 ml) for 48 h. The compound was separated from the filtrate by adding petroleum ether, then washed and dried.

$Al(OC_6H_4Cl)_3$ was obtained by different routes. (i) Aluminium(III) chloride (1.50 g, 0.011 mol) was refluxed with excess of *o*-chlorophenol (4.826 g, 0.038 mol) in benzene (100 ml) for more than 48 h till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. (ii) Aluminium(III) chloride (1.50 g, 0.011 mol) was refluxed with excess of *o*-chlorophenol (50ml) till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The compound so obtained was washed with benzene and dried under anhydrous conditions.

Dichloro aluminium phenoxide, $Al(OC_6H_5)_2Cl_2$, was prepared by refluxing aluminium(III) chloride (2.55 g, 0.019 mol) with phenol (1.805 g, 0.019 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml), till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. The compound so obtained was filtered, washed with benzene and dried.

Diphenoxyaluminium chloride, $Al(OC_6H_5)_2Cl$, was prepared by refluxing aluminium(III) chloride

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(2.10 g, 0.016 mol) with phenol (2.46 g, 0.036 mol) in benzene (100 ml) till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. The compound so obtained was filtered, washed with benzene and dried.

The compound aluminium(III)triphenylcarbinol of the composition $\text{Al}[\text{OC}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3]_3$ was prepared by reacting triphenylcarbinol (1 g) with sodium metal (2 g) and dry aluminium(III) chloride (8 g) in dry benzene. The contents were stirred by magnetic stirrer for more than 8 h and then refluxed for 2 h at 70° . The resulting solid so obtained was filtered, washed with benzene to remove excess triphenylcarbinol and finally dried under vacuum.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by elemental analysis. Aluminium in these compounds was estimated as Al_2O_3 and chlorine by Volhard method. Molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene were determined on a Elico conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) were scanned using double grating Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrophotometers. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Stanton AD-2 thermogravimetric balance. Determination of molecular weight of compounds was carried out cryoscopically by Beckmann method.

Results and Discussion

In order to ascertain the possible composition of various phenoxides of aluminium that could be formed from aluminium(IV) chloride, conductometric titrations between sodium and potassium phenoxides against aluminium(III) chloride have been carried out at $50^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ in phenol and in nitrobenzene at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. It is apparent from the conductance composition curves at the molar ratios 2 : 3, 3 : 1, 2 : 1 and 1 : 1. In the case of aluminium(III) chlorides, addition of alkali metal phenoxide results continuous increase in the conductance of the solution till the molar ratio $\text{MOPh}/\text{AlCl}_3$ reaches a value of 0.5 : 1. Further addition of sodium/potassium phenoxide results a continuous increase in the conductance of the solution till the molar ratio $\text{MOPh}/\text{AlCl}_3$ reaches a value of 2 : 1. There is further rise in the conductance of the solution on

addition of alkali metal phenoxide and on reaching the molar ratio 3 : 1 there is again a change in the trend of the rise in conductance of the solution. Possible mode of reactions depicting various molar ratios in the conductance composition curves may be explained as follows.

- (i) Upto molar ratio 0.5 : 1
 $2\text{AlCl}_3 + \text{KOC}_6\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{AlCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5) + \text{KCl}$
- (ii) Upto molar ratio 1 : 1
 $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{AlCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5) + \text{KOC}_6\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{AlCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 + \text{KCl}$
- (iii) Upto molar ratio 3 : 2
 $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{AlCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 + \text{KOC}_6\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3 + \text{KCl}$
- (iv) Upto molar ratio 2 : 1
 $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3 + \text{KOC}_6\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{AlCl}_2 \cdot (\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 + \text{KCl}$
- (v) Upto molar ratio 3 : 1
 $\text{AlCl}_2 \cdot (\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 + 2\text{KOC}_6\text{H}_5 \rightarrow 2\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3 + 2\text{KCl}$
- (vi) Upto molar ratio 4 : 1
 $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3 + \text{KOC}_6\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{K}^+ + \text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4^-$

The compounds isolated in the present study are high melting solids. They are moisture sensitive and quite stable in dry atmosphere. Most of them are soluble in organic solvents, such as benzene, acetone, phenols and nitrobenzene. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of compounds in nitrobenzene are quite low which excludes their possibility of being ionic. All the values are given in Table 1.

Determination of molecular weight in organic solvents has been helpful in establishing the polymeric nature of some of the metal phenoxides. Cryoscopy and ebulliometry in solvents, such as benzene, n-hexane and cyclopentane have been widely used which help to understand the structure of these phenoxides. The compounds $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_3$ have been found to be trimeric.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF ALUMINIUM(III) PHENOXIDES*

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
			Al	Cl		
$\text{AlCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$	White	320	13.13 (14.13)	37.02 (37.17)	183 (191)	0.0129
$\text{AlCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$	White	320	10.93 (10.80)	10.23 (10.40)	240 (248.5)	0.112
$\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$	White	300	8.76 (8.82)	—	301 (306)	1.68
$\text{Al}[\text{OC}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3]_3$	Light brown	300	3.65 (3.34)	—	794 (804)	1.99
$\text{Al}(\text{O}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_3$	Yellow	310	6.31 (6.12)	—	—	0.022
$\text{Al}(\text{O}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_3$	Dirty white	300	6.09 (7.58)	21.09 (26.00)	—	1.901

*All are solid.

Interestingly, aluminium(III) diphenoxychloride and aluminium phenoxydichloride have been found to be dimeric in benzene and nitrobenzene but the extent of association increases as the concentration of the solute increases the molecular association. But the phenoxide of composition $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ is only dimer. A change in the molecular complexity of various types of phenoxides may be due to the steric effect of triphenyl carbinol.

Their bands at 3500 cm^{-1} , assigned to OH stretching, is missing in the case of phenoxides of composition $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$, $\text{AlCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$, $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OCPh}_3)_3$ which supports the observation that hydrogen chloride gas is evolved during their preparations. The broad bands at 1362 and 1343 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\text{ring} + \delta_{\text{OH}}$ in phenol, disappear in these phenoxides. The sharp intense bands at 3052 and 3074 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ in phenol, are observed in the region 3045 - 3055 and 3068 - 3070 cm^{-1} which are almost at the same positions as in the parent phenol. The bands at 1608 , 1600 , 1502 and 1473 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in the phenolic ring, shift slightly to higher regions; possibly due to the increased ring conjugation brought about by the attachment to the metal atom. The bands at 1167 , 1151 , 1070 and 1026 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ stretching modes of the ring, remain unaltered in these phenoxides. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ stretching frequency shifts to lower spectral region by 50 - 60 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of these compounds. This may be attributed to the drainage of electrons from the ring to the metal through C-O bond.

Far-ir spectra of these compounds have been very helpful in throwing some light on their structures. In the case of the phenoxides of composition $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ sharp bands observed at 588 and 592 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the terminal $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ stretching modes while the bands at 528 and 529 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the

bridging $\text{Al}-\text{O}-\text{Al}$ stretching modes as these bands are expected to be at the lower spectral regions as compared to the terminal modes⁶. The other bands observed at 480 - 490 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the terminal Al-Cl stretching modes to the tetrahedral stereochemistry^{7,8}. No band assignable to the

bridging $\text{Al}-\text{Cl}-\text{Al}$ stretching mode has been observed which shows that bridging in these complexes is through phenoxy groups. Hence, the structure may be as follows.

In the case of phenoxides $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$, consideration of aluminium oxygen stretching mode is very helpful especially in the lower region to decide the

configuration of central metal atom. Two types of Al-O stretching modes have been observed in the spectrum of this phenoxide, *i.e.* 590 and 548 cm^{-1} . The one observed at 590 cm^{-1} is quite sharp and may be assigned to the terminal Al-O stretching modes while the other at 548 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the bridging Al-O stretching modes. The presence of two types of aluminium oxygen modes and trimeric nature suggest ring type structure for the compound $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$.

Similar structure may be proposed for $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_3$. Since molecular weight determinations have suggested that the phenoxide of composition $\text{Al}(\text{OCPh}_3)_3$ exists only as dimer and there are two types of Al-O stretching modes present in the molecules, therefore, a dimeric structure may be proposed as follows.

In order to explore the possible modes of decomposition of these phenoxides and to determine relative strength of bonds, thermogravimetric analysis of these compounds were carried out under atmospheric pressure. Different intermediates have been postulated merely on the basis of the weight changes noted from the T.G.A. curves. Although the final product in all phenoxides studied to be Al_2O_3 , it is difficult to comment precisely on the nature of the intermediates formed. The possible modes of decomposition may be postulated as follows.

In the case of compound $\text{AlCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Al}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ at temperature below 100° , it does not show any loss in weight. Around 180° one mole of chlorobenzene is lost. At 290° it further disproportionates to form diphenyl ether and around $850-900^\circ$ alumina is formed. Possible modes of decomposition is postulated as follows.

Composition of the final product has been established by elemental analyses.

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